

APPLYING INNOVATIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES AND TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Today, communities are increasingly facing rapid and profound changes and tensions that affect the social, economic, and political aspects of life. The role of education has also become questionable in the millennial era. A matter of fact, 21st century education requires a gradual shift in curriculum construction focusing on the transferable competencies that learners need to develop in instructional settings. In today's knowledge-based, types of skills and competencies that students need to gain are different from in the past. Emphasizing the communicative competence is one of the most influential developments in language education. The implementation of communicative activities in EFL/ESL classroom prepares learners to use English in the world beyond based on their own needs, interests and opportunities.

Approval of the roadmap for the development of higher education in Uzbekistan until 2030, setting priorities for systematic reform, improving the quality of education and training of skilled professionals, and modernizing the education system to support social and economic progress through advanced educational technologies is essential. The modern era has witnessed tremendous changes in all walks of life and technology has no exemption. Technological innovations in the twenty-first century have brought a drastic change in the lives of human beings. Because of these technological innovations, human beings have achieved a great progress in their respective fields. Due to the new technological innovations, there is a great progress in almost all the fields. In the field of education also, we can witness several changes. These drastic changes have also a great influence in teaching English. It is evident that technology has become a part of teaching and learning. Because of novelty of these technological innovations, the teaching of English has paved way for radical changes.

In the 21st century, information technologies are actively used in all spheres of human activity, including education. With the advent of the first personal computers, teachers began to use them to intensify the learning process as a means of visualization, a tool for developing skills, a source of additional information, etc.

The progress of technical progress, more and more advanced technical means appeared, which had a significant linguodidactic potential. Today, in the practice of teaching foreign languages, a wide range of technical means are used, both stationary (for example, a computer, interactive whiteboard) and mobile (tablet computers, smartphones), which are combined under the concept of "digital technologies". The emergence of these technical means also influenced the ways of presenting information, which today is most often presented in a multimedia format, that is, in several forms at the same time: text, graphic, video, audio, interactive. Thus, modern technologies used in teaching foreign languages can be combined under the term "multimedia and digital technologies".

Among the linguistic views from the important directions of modern linguistics aim to determine the laws and principles of using language units as a means of speech activity and to determine the characteristics of linguistic phenomena related to the occurrence of linguistic phenomena in real communication conditions. The relevance of this research is, on the one hand, focused on the analysis of the semantic-structural features of the language system and its main unit, the word.

It is necessary to pay attention to scientific research in the study of speech in English linguistics. It was considered that the words in the sentence in "grammar", which is considered the main source, are connected with each other, that each of them performs a grammatical function in the sentence - the function of a sentence fragment. It has been studied how the parts of the sentence are divided into two - primary parts (possessive, participle) and secondary parts (complement, determiner, case).

However, the long-term practice of using various similar technologies in teaching foreign languages shows that by themselves they do not make the learning process more effective. To use multimedia and digital technologies to their full potential, it is necessary to develop a special methodology.

However, due to the active progress of technological progress and the emergence of new types of multimedia and digital technologies against the backdrop of changing educational paradigms, the practice of using these technologies is still ahead of theory. Moreover, the existing research in this area is mainly focused on the methodology of teaching a foreign language to students.

As a result, the modern classrooms have been equipped with the latest technological equipment. Teachers as well as learners make use of these latest innovations to achieve the desired results in their teaching-learning process. The teachers of English can make use of these latest technologies to motivate, encourage and attract the modern learners in grasping the content with utmost attention and concentration. The teachers of English have to make use of the available technology in their classrooms and adopt all the possible novel techniques, methods and approaches in order to make their classrooms lively and dynamic. The learners of English should concentrate more on the content that is being taught in the classrooms by the teachers and make the teaching-learning a fruitful one. The main responsibility is on the shoulders of the teachers to use the material according to the needs and interests of the learners by using the modern technology in the English classrooms.

The communicative approach in language teaching starts from a theory of language as communication. The goal of language teaching is to develop what referred to as

"communicative competence." There are following directions in communicative language teaching:

Focuses on language as a medium of communication. Recognizes that all communication has a social purpose - learner has something to say or find out.

The teacher sets up a situation that students are likely to encounter in real life. The real-life simulations change from day to day. Students' motivation to learn comes from their desire to communicate in meaningful ways about meaningful topics.

Communicative approach places great emphasis on helping students use the target language in a variety of contexts and places great emphasis on learning language functions. This means that successfully learning a foreign language is assessed in terms of how well learners have developed their communicative competence.

More emphasis on active modes of learning, including pair work and group-work

Emphasis on oral and listening skills in the classroom. Not just hearing teacher, but having personal contact themselves with language, practicing sounds themselves, permutating sentence patterns and getting chance to make mistakes and learn from doing so.

Makes use of topical items with which pupils are already familiar in their own language - motivates pupils arouses their interest and leads to more active participation.

Communicative approach seeks to use authentic resources. More interesting and motivating. In Foreign language classroom, authentic texts serve as partial substitute for community of native speaker. Newspaper and magazine articles, poems, manuals, recipes, telephone directories, videos, all can be exploited in variety of ways.

Communicative approach is much more pupil-orientated, because dictated by pupils' needs and interests.

The principles of communicative teaching are following:

- Teaching is learner-centered and responsive to the students' need and interests.
- The target language is acquired through interactive communicative use that encourages the negotiations of meaning.
- Genuinely meaningful language use is emphasized, along with unpredictability, risk-taking, and choice-making.
- The formal properties of language are never treated in isolation from use. language forms are always addressed within a communicative context.
- There is exposure to examples of authentic language from the target language community.
- The students are encouraged to discover the forms and structures of language for themselves.
- There is a whole-language approach in which the four traditional language skills (speaking, listening, reading, and writing) are integrated.

Different aspects of the communicative approach:

Learner-centered instruction: As opposed to teacher centered, it assumes the student is the most importance person in the class.

Cooperative and collaborative learning: This is opposed to a competitive classroom, where students work against each other to achieve a goal.

Interactive learning: Because communication is interactive, so then must be language instruction. This means that we both listen and speak when we communicate, and that both

affect each other. Thus, we should prepare our students to be able to engage in negotiation of meaning with another person in a series of gives and takes in the real world.

Content-based instruction: This is the study of content at the same time as the study of language. For example, students can learn about a topic that is important to them while they develop their language skills.

Task-based instruction: This is a method of instruction that provides for students to problem-solve, write and perform role-plays or come to an agreed conclusion alone, in groups or pairs with the goal always being meaningful communication.

Communicative approach of teaching has the following **three advantages:**

1. The interaction between students and teachers. Communicative teaching is becoming increasingly clear feature is the change in the way as the internship, students develop the subject, initiative and become increasingly important. Teacher-student relationship is an interactive, harmonious relationship, rather than the traditional education, the kind of master-servant relationship.

2. To impart the basic knowledge and ability to skillfully combine the development. The communicative teaching emphasizes the learner's cognitive ability and operational capabilities, which allow the students themselves to think about and express their views, thus trained in real life the ability to use language to communicate.

3. Greatly enhanced the student's interest. Communicative teaching students to participate in, sometimes accompanied by scenes or simulated scenarios, so that students more close to life, the students became the main character, naturally they were interested in the English language, to learn English as a pleasure.

The communicative approach is based on the idea that in order to learn a second language successfully, you have to communicate real meaning. Thus, when learners are involved in real communication, their natural strategies for language acquisition will be active and used, and this will allow them to learn to use the language. Learner autonomy is best fostered when students have control at the highest possible level of curriculum design. Thus, we can conclude that one of the areas in which additional research is needed is the effective implementation of social media at the level of course design. Rather than a simple aid to activities, social media should be driving the way courses are designed. Moreover, with its increasing popularity, the influence of social media is only going to continue. By accepting it as a communicative tool and an important part of the learning process, teachers will bring their classes in line with a modernising society. Focusing on how social can be used in line with teaching philosophies and frameworks will give it a greater role in the language classroom. In this manner, the previously mentioned practical issues of teacher training and accessibility can be much improved if the technology is embedded into theoretical frameworks. Playing a role in course and syllabus design will also give CALL and social media more potential as tools to benefit the EFL environment and to develop as a philosophy, as society itself develops its own philosophies and trends in communication. A natural progression of this work, which could produce interesting findings, is to scrutinize the influence of social media, in the same sense as CALL, on EFL material design and delivery.

References:

1. Brandl, K. (2008). *Communicative Language Teaching in Action*, New Jersey, Pearson Prentice Hall.

2. Brumfit, C. J. (1984). Communicative methodology in language teaching: The Roles of Fluency and Accuracy. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
3. Spada, N. (2007). Communicative Language Teaching: Current Status and Future Prospects. International Hand Book of English Language Teaching (Part I). New York, Springer.
4. Newmark, P. (1981). Approaches to Translation (Language Teaching Methodology Senes). Oxford, Pergamon Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263100005222>

